

📍 9-10th July, 2017 at FIIT STU, Bratislava, Slovakia

Collocated with UMAP 2017

[HOME](#) [CALLS](#) ▾ [REGISTRATION](#) [PROGRAM](#) ▾ [PROCEEDINGS](#) [VENUE](#) ▾

[COMMITTEES](#) ▾ [CONTACTS](#)

ABOUT

The Semantic and Social Media Adaptation and Personalization (SMAP) workshop is the evolution of the **Semantic Media Adaptation** and **Personalization** initiative, which was founded during the summer of 2006 in an effort to discuss the state of the art, recent advances and future perspectives for semantic media adaptation and personalization. However, as **Social Media** applications have substantially transformed the way organizations, communities, and individuals interact, we have the scopes of SMAP extended towards this new trend, seeking to bring together researchers from the social web as well as from the semantic web communities.

After eleven successful workshops starting from Athens, and then London, Prague, San Sebastian, Limassol, Vigo, Luxembourg, Bayonne, Corfu, Trento and Thessaloniki, the SMAP workshop series has been consolidated as a reference event in order to discuss about the newest advances in the field.

Character of Smap

Those familiar with the SMAP initiative and workshops will find it easy to identify the features that express the actual heart of SMAP, features that you can certainly expect to find in SMAP 2017.

Firstly, the scope of SMAP is clearly well-defined and focused, as it is intended to be the annual meeting of the international semantic and social media adaptation and personalization community. The workshop entertains papers that fall solely within the same scope, and therefore cannot and should not be assigned to independent parallel sessions; thus SMAP will remain a single track workshop, offering participants the opportunity to attend every single presentation.

Secondly, the nature of SMAP is purely academic and there is no thought of financial profit for any of the organizing parties. In this manner conference fees are set so that the event marginally breaks even. Special care is taken for students attending the event and wishing to benefit from the discussions held in its scope.

Finally, although the SMAP community is very focused, it is also very open. If you find our topics interesting we will be glad to meet and welcome you.

Past conferences:

SMAP 2017 – Bratislava, Slovakia [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2016 – Thessaloniki, Greece [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2015 – Trento, Italy [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2014 – Corfu, Greece [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2013 – Bayonne, France [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2012 – Luxembourg, Luxembourg [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2011 – Vigo, Spain [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2010 – Limassol, Cyprus [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2009 – San Sebastian, Spain [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2008 – Prague, Czech Republic [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2007 – London, United Kingdom [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

SMAP 2006 – Athens, Greece [IEEE Xplore Proceedings]

FIIT STU, 9-10TH JULY,
2017

SMAP2017 – 12th International
Workshop on Semantic and Social
Media Adaptation and Personalization

LATEST NEWS

SMAP Proceedings available
September 3, 2017

Photo gallery published
July 18, 2017

Detailed conference program was
published
June 20, 2017

Sunday Keynote
June 5, 2017

TAGS

[attendance](#) [cultural heritage](#)

[keynote speaker](#) [program proposals](#)

[registration](#) [SMAP2017](#)

[Special sessions](#) [Website](#)